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Light Touch²

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GNC

Concept

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Deflection

System

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Target

Light Touch²

Mission, Control, Navigation

AdAM

Roadmap

Target

Target

- Initial target selection based on orbital elements, size and Orbit Condition Code (OCC).
 - ~9,500 NEOS known today, 189 with $Q < 1.4$ AU & $q > 0.7$ AU, and only 10 with $D \sim 4$ m considering $p_v = 0.154$.
 - OCC > 4 are equivalent to “lost objects”. → Only 2 left.

DESIGNATION	PHA (Y/N)	H	q (AU)	Q (AU)	i (deg)	D (km) ($p_v=0.154$)	OCC
2008 JL24	N	29.572	0.927631	1.148906	0.550106	0.004124	3
2006 RH120	N	29.527	1.007964	1.058540	0.595266	0.004211	1

2008JL24

2006RH120

Orbital Elements at Epoch 2456200.5 (2012-Sep-30.0) TDB
Reference: JPL 10 (heliocentric ecliptic J2000)

Element	Value	Uncertainty (1-sigma)	Units
e	.106559869181477	7.2705e-06	
a	1.03826844970543	2.8956e-06	AU
q	.9276306995295643	5.0396e-06	AU
i	.5501064109470443	4.6053e-05	deg
node	225.822449694026	0.00026854	deg
peri	281.9655686889383	0.00038643	deg
M	124.186109529154	0.0073006	deg
t_p	2456067.198991958747 (2012-May-19.69899196)	0.0072788	JED
period	386.4229508179025	0.0016165	d
	1.06	4.426e-06	yr
n	.9316216835413743	3.8973e-06	deg/d
Q	1.148906199881296	3.2042e-06	AU

Rotation ~ 18 rev/h

Orbital Elements at Epoch 2456200.5 (2012-Sep-30.0) TDB
Reference: JPL 45 (heliocentric ecliptic J2000)

Element	Value	Uncertainty (1-sigma)	Units
e	.02447403062284801	4.2401e-05	
a	1.033252056035198	1.0251	AU
q	1.007964213574672	1	AU
i	.5952660003048117	9.4379e-05	deg
node	51.14334927580387	3.8304e-05	deg
peri	10.14353817485877	0.092984	deg
M	221.2498016727181	206.48	deg
t_p	2456348.356001016605 (2013-Feb-24.85600102)	1	JED
period	383.6258326667335	570.89	d
	1.05	1.563	yr
n	.9384143854377558	1.3965	deg/d
Q	1.058539898495724	1.0502	AU

Rotation ~ 21.8 rev/h

Target

- Target observability from Earth

Table 5: NEO properties and next observation opportunities according to NHATS⁵

Object Designation	Orbit ID	ΔH (mag)	Estimated Diameter (m)	OCC	Min. delta-V [delta-V, dur.] (km/s), (d)	Min. Duration [delta-V, dur.] (km/s), (d)	Viable Trajectories	Next Optical Opportunity (yyyy-mm [Vp])	Next Arecibo Radar Opportunity (yyyy-mm [SNRR])	Next Goldstone Radar Opportunity (yyyy-mm [SNRR])
(2008 JL24)	10	29.6	2.1 - 9.5	3	4.628, 394	11.791, 82	904797	none	none	none
(2006 RH120)	45	29.5	2.2 - 10	1	3.989, 450	11.323, 42	1283738	2028-06 [23.9]	none	none

- Target observability from S/C

Fig: Uncertainty in asteroid position for 2008 JL24 (left) and 2006 RH120 (right) as a function of time (MJD2000).

2006 RH120 allows a reliable rendezvous considering both ephemeris uncertainties and future optical opportunities.

Light Touch²

Ablation Process

- Energy balance:

$$\left(E_v + \frac{1}{2} \bar{v}^2 + C_p (T_s - T_0) + C_v (T_s - T_0) \right) \dot{\mu} = P_I - Q_{RAD} - Q_{COND}$$

- Ejection velocity dependent on temperature: $\bar{v} = \sqrt{\frac{8k_b T_s}{\pi M_a}}$

- Integrated mass flow over the spot including rotation:

$$\dot{m} = 2V_{rot} \int_0^{y_{max}} \int_{t_{in}}^{t_{out}} \frac{1}{E_v^*} \left((P_I - Q_{rad}) - \left(\sqrt{\frac{ck\rho}{\pi}} (T_{subl} - T_0) \right) \sqrt{\frac{1}{t}} \right) dt dy$$

- Thrust model includes a scattering factor:

$$F_{sub} = \lambda \bar{v} \dot{m}$$

- Input power dependent on system efficiency:

$$P_I = \tau \tau_g \alpha_M \eta_P \eta_L \eta_S \frac{P_{1AU} A_{SA}}{A_{spot} R_{AU}^2}$$

Contamination Model

- Density dependent on elevation angle distance:

$$\rho(r, \theta) = \rho^* K_P \frac{d_{SPOT}^2}{(2r + d_{SPOT})^2} \left[\cos \left(\frac{\pi \theta}{2\theta_{MAX}} \right) \right]^{k-1}$$

- Thickness of the layer of contaminant dependent on view factor and mass flow:

$$\frac{dh}{dt} = \frac{2\bar{v}\rho}{\rho_l} \cos \psi_{vf}$$

- Beer–Lambert law for light absorption:

$$\tau = e^{-2\eta h}$$

- Key coefficients experimentally derived using asteroid analogous materials

Focusing and Beam Control

$$z_R = \frac{\pi w_0^2}{\lambda_b}$$

Beam behaviour of a 1070nm fibre laser and an f=50m optic

Momentum Coupling

$$C_m = \frac{F_{sub}}{P_{IN}} \quad P_{IN} = \tau \eta_P \eta_S \frac{P_{1AU} A}{R_{AU}^2}$$

Mass Efficiency

$\eta_L=0.55$, Laser Cm=1.1628e-5N/W, $I_{sp}=3325s$, EP Cm=1.63e-005N/W

$\eta_L=0.55$, Laser Cm=1.1628e-5N/W, $I_{sp}=1640s$, EP Cm=2.79e-005N/W

$\eta_L=0.55$, Laser Cm=1.4e-005N/W, $I_{sp}=3325s$, EP Cm=1.63e-005N/W

$\eta_L=0.55$, Laser Cm=1.4e-005N/W, $I_{sp}=1640s$, EP Cm=2.79e-005N/W

Efficiency analysis

Thrusting time required to achieve 1 m/s for different shoot shooting distances

Deflection Result

Assuming 860W at 1AU the target Δv can be achieved in about half a year.

Mission, Control, Navigation

Mission: Interplanetary Trajectory and LW

- Opportunities in 2027 (nominal) and 2028 (backup)

Earth Departure	V_{inf} (km/s)	DSM date (Fraction ToF)	DSM Δv (km/s)	Asteroid Arrival	Arr Δv (km/s)	ToF (Days)	Total Δv (km/s)
8/11/2027	0.5403	N/A	0	9/09/2028	0.4871	306.5	3.677

- Preliminary analysis assumes escape 400x400 orbit
- Low Δv requirements during transfer and arrival

- Wide LW

- 1 month \rightarrow less 1% extra costs

Mission: Launcher & Propulsion Trade-off

- Launcher and propulsion trade-off:
 - VEGA to LEO / PSLV to LEO *with* Off-the shelf PRM / Integrated SC / Solid motor
 - **PSLV XL to GTO** *with* **Biprop** / EP
 - (Ariane 5 ECA tertiary payload) **costs**

- Refined trajectory

Non-Sphericity	8 Zonal, 8 Tesseral
S/C Initial Mass	1074 kg (maxi for PSLV XL)
Third Body	Moon, Earth
SRP	A: 7.4 m ² C _R = 1.5
Dep. Conditions	GTO: 200 x 36 000 km , 18°
Specific Impulse	321 sec
Thrust	450 N

- Final mass > 690 kg

Manoeuvre	Δv [m/s]
Departure	792
DSM	186
Arrival	395

GNC Strategy and Analysis

- NEO Mission
 - References - Hayabusa, Marco Polo, Rosetta, NEAR, Stardust
 - Relies heavily in optical navigation
 - Dynamics – 3 body problem, SRP, asteroid rotation,
 - Need for combined approach strategy definition and GNC analysis
- AdAM
 - 2006RH120 is approximately 4 m diameter, 130 Ton, 31 Visual Mag
 - Gravity pull at 50 m range is $2 \mu\text{N}$, 1 order of magnitude below SRP $40 \mu\text{N}$, 6 orders of magnitude lower than for Hayabusa's Itokawa (382 mN). Implications
 - Dynamics modelling/decoupling → GNC algorithms modularity
 - Strategy – no stable terminator orbits → unstable hold points
 - Safety → spacecraft is barely pulled towards asteroid
 - Can be detected at $40 \times 10^3 \text{ Km}$ - Don Quijote's 160-meter-wide 2002AT4 could be detected from $2500 \times 10^3 \text{ Km}$
 - Duration of operations Hayabusa/Marco Polo – Sample Return; Rosetta – Orbit, Release Lander; NEAR – Orbit, Touch-Down; Stardust - Flyby. AdAM - Actively perturbing the asteroid from a hold point for 2 years (while counter-acting forces and trailing the asteroid) → component life-time, robustness
- FF / RV / Debris Removal as add. reference (ATV, Proba, MSR)

GNC Strategy

- **Early Encounter** (Launch + 296 Days)
 - RVM (main engine, Δv 391 m/s) @60 000 Km distance
 - Scan, Acquire LOS, relative accuracy from ~5000 Km to 10 Km
- **Far Approach** (11 Days)
 - Reduce relative distance from **5000 Km to 10 Km**
 - Improve relative accuracy from **10 Km to 1 Km** , 1 mm/s
 - (accuracy improves through Dog leg LOS observation + Radiometric)
- **Close Approach** (11 Days)
 - Acquire Ranging Sensor, early validation of GNC functions, tackle SRP
 - Approach from **10 Km to 1 Km** through dog-leg in 6 days through 6 WP
 - Accuracy in range direction improves to **20 m , 0.1 mm/s**
 - Final approach segment from **1 Km to 300 m** in 6 hours, where ranging sensor is acquired.
 - Accuracy in range direction improves to **<1 m , < 0.1 mm/s**
 - SRP causes 5 Km drift in 4 days → close approach is autonomous (through station keeping hold points)
- **Transition to Operation** (26 days)
 - GNC callibration, Test Station Keeping, Fine Asteroid Ephemeris Characterization
 - Station keeping with increasingly narrow boxes, from 300 to 50 m to NEO
- **Operations – Testing and Calibration** (2 months)
 - Supervised used of laser for periods of minutes, then hours, weeks and month
- **Operations – Nominal** - 90 days ablation + 10 days orbital determination campaigns

Early Encounter

- **Ephemeris Uncertainty**

- 5 000 Km
- 2 m/s

- **Detection/Scanning**

(13.5 rel mag)

- 60 000 Km Nominally
- 30 000 Km Worst Case

- **RVM**

- Illuminated approach
- Minimize drift in the FOV
- Observe NEO from 90(+30) deg

Approach

Far Approach

- LOS + Radiometric - based Navigation (NAC)
- Lower the Range, Improve Accuracy
- 1st Segment – Gravity-Gradient , 2nd SRP

Close Approach

- Autonomous GNC
- Dog-leg manoeuvres
- Improvement on range through LOS, Δv / LOS rate , brightness/size
- Predictive Guidance through WP
- **HP** at 1 Km, approach to 300 meters
- Acquisition of ranging sensor

Transition to Operations

- Full Metrology Acquired
- Asteroid is 300 000 pixels in NAC, 10 in WAC
- Autonomous Station-Keeping

- **Calibrate**
 - WAC , NAC , STR for LOS, starry background
 - Range/Range Rate – (size of asteroid, rangefinder, shadow)
- **Characterize Asteroid**
 - Size, Rotational State
 - Features
- **Build Thrust**
 - Validate Procedures,
 - Assess GNC Algorithms Performances
- **Orbit Determination**
 - Radiometric measurements
 - Relative metrology
 - <0.4 AU from Earth

**Followed by series of
Ablation Tests**

Proximity Operations

Control Box

- $\pm 1\text{m}$ range wrt surface
- $\pm 0.5\text{ m}$ lateral

Metrology

- Image - LOS to CoB
- Range to Surface

Strategy

- 6 Days Ablation, 1 day data relay
- For 90 days, then 10 days radiometric nav

	Force μN	Variation	τ
SRP	38	20%	7 d
Recoil	3.3	1%	1 m
Gravity	1.7	10 %	5 m
Impingement	20 (6)	20%	1 h
Deflection	42.3	20%	1 d
Total (trailing)	62.8		
Total (radial)	25.5		

GNC Architecture and Hardware

NAC

- Main Approach Sensor
- Rotational State
- Fitted with FEIC

WAC

- Proximity (LOS)
- Calibration

Laser Rangefinder

- Low-Power, Low-weight (wrt to LIDAR, Radar)
- Proximity – range to surface

Camera	Pixel [μ rad]	FOV	Range [Km] (worst case)	Mass
Galileo Avionica VBNC	200	70	10	0.6 kg
Marco Polo R NAC	15	1.7	30 000	6 kg

LRF	To qualify
Accuracy	10 cm
Power	<2 W
Mass	0.5 K
Rate	1*MHz
Range	500 m
Bandwidth	920 nm

GNC Architecture

- Modular
- Robust

Radiometric Orbit Determination

- Range, Doppler from Harwel*
- Δ DOR from DSA
 - (3 x 2 in nominal mission)
- Combined with relative metrology to obtain NEO orbit

GNC Modules

Asteroid Rotation On-line Estimation

- Displacement of each FP

$$\begin{bmatrix} u \\ v \end{bmatrix} = \frac{f}{x_C} \begin{bmatrix} y_C \\ z_C \end{bmatrix}$$

c_P

c_{O_B}

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{u} \\ \dot{v} \end{bmatrix} = M \left(f, \begin{matrix} \text{from nav} \\ c_P, c_{O_B} \end{matrix} \right) \begin{bmatrix} {}^C V_{B/C} \\ {}^C \omega_{B/C} \end{bmatrix}$$

- Invert Matrix (or LSQ, etc)

$$\begin{matrix} \text{from nav} \\ \begin{bmatrix} {}^C V_{B/C} \\ {}^C \omega_{B/C} \end{bmatrix} \end{matrix} = \begin{bmatrix} M(f, c_{P_1}, c_{O_B}) \\ \vdots \\ M(f, c_{P_N}, c_{O_B}) \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \dot{u}_1 \\ \dot{v}_1 \\ \vdots \\ \dot{u}_N \\ \dot{v}_N \end{bmatrix}$$

10 tracked points
(only need to track
from 2 instants)

Rotation Estimate FFT Approach

- Complex Spectrum of Position of points on the body (Fourier transform)
- Camera and LRF to detect points' relative position
- Rotations around two axis
- 2 distinct frequencies (4 frequencies in the spectrum)

$$\mathbf{p}' = \mathbf{a} \cos(\theta_1) + \mathbf{b} \sin(\theta_1) + \mathbf{c} \cos(\theta_2) + \mathbf{d} \sin(\theta_2) + \mathbf{e} \cos(\theta_1 + \theta_2) + \mathbf{f} \sin(\theta_1 + \theta_2) + \mathbf{g} \cos(\theta_1 - \theta_2) + \mathbf{h} \sin(\theta_1 - \theta_2) + \mathbf{i}$$

- Intersection of the two axis identifies the CG
- No needs to know inertia and mass of the asteroid

Example

- 21 rotations/hour around z-axis (5.833E-3Hz)
- 1 rotation/hour around y-axis (2.778E-4Hz)
- One image every 10 seconds
- 4 points tracked per image
- Observation period 2 hours

- Exact determination of frequency
- Rotational axis
- $z_est = [0.009 \ 0.054 \ 0.998]$;
- $y_est = [0.317 \ 0.948 \ 0.000]$;

Proximity Navigation and Control

- Relative perturbed spacecraft motion described in the Hill reference frame:

$$\ddot{\mathbf{x}} = -\mathbf{a}_{r_a} - 2\mathbf{v} \times \dot{\mathbf{x}} - \dot{\mathbf{v}} \times \mathbf{x} - \mathbf{v} \times (\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{x}) - \frac{\mu_{sun}}{r_{sc}^3} (\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{x}_{r_a}) - \frac{\mu_a}{\delta r^3} \mathbf{x} + \nabla U + \frac{\mathbf{F}_{sc}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}_{r_a})}{m_{sc}}$$

- U second order gravity field potential
- \mathbf{F}_{sc} force acting on the spacecraft
 - Laser recoil
 - Solar radiation pressure
 - Plume impingement
- \mathbf{a}_{r_a} relative acceleration of the reference frame

$$\ddot{\mathbf{r}}_a = -\frac{\mu_{sun}}{r_a^3} \mathbf{r}_a - \frac{\mu_{sc}}{\delta r^3} \mathbf{x}_a + \mathbf{a}_{laser}$$

- tugging effect
- \mathbf{a}_{laser} acceleration from laser ablation

- Control box to maximize the effectiveness of laser

$$\mathbf{f}' = \mathbf{v}_{in}^{est} + \Delta \mathbf{v}_{corr} + \mathbf{a}_{est} t = 0$$

$$\mathbf{d}_f = \mathbf{d}_{in}^{est} + (\mathbf{v}_{in}^{est} + \Delta \mathbf{v}_{corr}) t + \mathbf{a}_{est} \frac{t^2}{2}$$

- $\Delta \mathbf{v}_{corr}$ corrective impulse bit

Need to estimate

- Spacecraft relative position and velocity
- Perturbative acceleration acting

- On board orbit determination by processing measurements from

- Camera
- Lidar Range Finder

Proximity Navigation and Control

- Example Trailing Configuration

- Control Δv

Trailing Configuration
Station keeping for 1 year

Radial Configuration
Station keeping for 1 year

-Radial configuration
less demanding than
the trailing one

How to measure the efficiency of a deflection strategy?

Two quantities can be measured:

- Integral of the acceleration imparted onto the asteroid

$$\delta v_I = \int_{\text{start ablation}}^{\text{stop ablation}} \frac{F_{\text{sub}}(t)}{m_{\text{NEO}}(t)} dt$$

- Variation of position and velocity with respect to the nominal orbit of the asteroid

Quantity of interest in an actual deflection mission

- strongly affected by the thrust direction
- the starting point of the deflection action and the orbital characteristics of the asteroid.

Estimating Δv imparted onto the asteroid

2. Measurement from OD

- Measurement of the deflected position of the asteroid at the end of the thrusting arc, with respect to its nominal position (through orbit determination campaign).
- Compute the delta velocity equivalent to a continuous thrust arc through the use of relative motion equations

$$\delta v_{measured} = \Phi^{-1} \delta r(t_{measure}) \quad [1]$$

Φ^{-1} transition matrix of the relative motion equations
 $\delta r(t_{measure})$ relative position of the asteroid with respect to its nominal one at the time of measure

- Dependent on range measurements
- Dependent on time interval between ODS
- Dependent on thrust direction

[1] Vasile M. and Colombo C., "Optimal Impact Strategies for Asteroid Deflection", Journal of Guidance, Control and Dynamics, Vol. 31, No. 4, July–Aug. 2008, pp. 858–872, doi: 10.2514/1.33432.

Estimating Δv imparted onto the asteroid

- Monte Carlo analysis considering errors in the determination of position and velocity at each orbit determination campaign:
 - (Error 1) 500 m in position and 0.5 mm/s in velocity
 - (Error 2) 1.5 km in position and 1 mm/s in velocity
 - (Error 3) 10 km in position and 10 mm/s in velocity
 - (Error 4) 5 km in position and 2 mm/s in velocity

Estimating Δv imparted onto the asteroid

- Proposed methods:
 - Δv given by the integral of the acceleration from the laser ablation

$$\delta \mathbf{v}_I = \int_{\text{start ablation}}^{\text{stop ablation}} \frac{\mathbf{F}_{sub}(t)}{m_{NEO}(t)} dt \quad \longrightarrow \quad \delta \mathbf{v}_I = \int_{\text{start ablation}}^{\text{stop ablation}} \mathbf{a}_{laser}^{estimated} dt$$

- High fidelity model for perturbations (recoil, asteroid's gravity, and solar radiation pressure)
- Force from the plume exerted on the same direction of the asteroid acceleration
- Camera+LRF+ impact sensor to estimate plume ejecta force

Acceleration - Trailing Configuration

Acceleration - Radial Configuration

	Radial Configuration		Trailing configuration	
Control box	20 cm	50 cm	20 cm	50 cm
Integral error	1.6%	1.2%	0.68%	0.49%

AdAM

Primary Payload

- Diode-pumped fibre laser system
 - Overall efficiency of 55 %, operating temperature 10 C
 - Focal length of 50 m [spacecraft-to-asteroid distance]
 - 860 W, with a spot size radius between 0.8-1 mm
 - Surface power density 428-274 MW/m²
 - Mass derived from space qualified reflective telescopes [HiRise reflective telescope] and perceived laser development for the 2025+ timeframe [DARPA, nLIGHT]
 - Optics 10 kg, laser 9.9 kg
 - Optical scheme is based on a simple combined beam expansion and focusing telescope

- Impact Sensor
 - Upon impact, used to measure the momentum created by the ejecta
 - Consist of a thin aluminium diaphragm with piezoelectric transducers
 - Heritage from Rosetta (GIADA) and PROBA-1 (DEBIE instrument)
 - 2.5 kg, 4 W

Laser System Schematic

Opportunistic Payload Selection

- Ablation results in the volumetric removal and ejection of deeply situated and currently inaccessible subsurface material.
[Gibbings, Vasile et al, 2012]
- Raman/Laser-Induced Breakdown Spectrometer
 - Best complements the laser ablation process
 - Single science objective
 - Measure the spectral emission and intensity of the ejecta plume
 - Measure the elemental composition, quality and concentration
 - Heritage from the ExoMars Rover, flight model [2 kg, 30 W] and pioneering technological development in laser sources, optical elements and spectrometers
- Supported by the operations of the WAC and NAC
 - Shape model, topographical profile, rotational state
 - Derivation of bulk density and mass

Design Drivers

- Cost
 - Low cost launch/transfer
 - Vega to LEO + LISA PRM not possible due to mass
 - PSLV to GTO offers sufficient mass and low cost
 - Low cost ground station
 - High performance communications subsystem
- Escaping from GTO
 - Relatively high Δv
 - Limit transfer time and passes through radiation belts
 - Bipropellant propulsion system
 - Relatively high fuel mass
 - Relatively high structure mass

Mass Budget

SysNova Mass Budget	Current Mass (kg)	Design Maturity Margin (%)	Maximum Mass (kg)
Data Handling	17.1	10.9%	18.9
Power	68.8	16.4%	80.1
Communications	37.7	8.8%	41.0
GNC & AOCS	39.5	7.9%	42.5
Structure and	100.0	20.0%	120.0
Thermal	13.0	20.0%	15.6
Propulsion	59.9	12.3%	67.3
Payload	35.5	19.4%	42.4
SPACECRAFT DRY TOTAL	371.4	15.2%	427.9
Harness	30.0	20.0%	35.9
DRY TOTAL (incl. Harness)			463.8
System Mass Margin		20.0%	92.8
DRY TOTAL (incl. 20% System Margin)			556.6
Propellant			405.2
SPACECRAFT WET MASS			961.8
Launch Vehicle Capability - PSLV GTO			974.0
Launch Vehicle Margin - PSLV GTO			12.2
Mass Margin % - PSLV GTO			1.3%

Power Budget

SysNova Power Budget	Current Power (W)	Design Maturity Margin (%)	Maximum Power (W)
Payload	895.0	19.7%	1071.0
GNC & AOCS	159.3	8.1%	172.2
Data Handling	46.9	11.0%	52.1
Power	0.0	0.0%	0.0
Communications	57.0	5.0%	59.9
Thermal	40.0	20.0%	48.0
Propulsion	0.0	0.0%	0.0
Total	1198.2	17.1%	1403.1
PCDU		10.0%	140.3
Harness		2.0%	28.1
Total Including PCDU and Harness			1571.5
System Power Margin		20.0%	314.3
Total Including 20% System Margin			1885.8

Downlink and Ground Segment

- Nominal science operations is the driving case with an 8 hour downlink once every 7 days
- Baseline system includes:
 - 1.3m X-band HGA
 - 160W Tx Output Power
 - 12m Rx antenna at Harwell
- Supports the required data rate of 23.5kbps at end of nominal operations
 - Link margin of 9.2dB
- Can also support the required data rate of 8kbps until the end of the 3 year mission lifetime
 - Link margin of 8.5dB

Radial Configuration

Trailing/Leading Configuration

Improved Solution

1. Low-mass low-power laser range finder instead of the LIDAR
2. Reduced power input to the laser down to 480W
3. Optimised spacecraft mass:
 - a. Improved thermal system mass
 - b. Improved structural mass
 - c. Optimised propellant mass
 - d. Improved power system mass
4. Same margin approach as for the second iteration

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Improved Solution

2006RH120, Start at t_{int}

A reduction in the input power to the laser leads to an increase of the deflection time to over 80% of the period of the asteroid.

The delivered thrust level fluctuates between 4 and 5.1 mN

2006RH120, Start at t_{int}

Improved Solution

SysNova Mass Budget	Current Mass (kg)	Design Maturity Margin (%)	Maximum Mass (kg)
Data Handling Subsystem	17.1	10.9%	18.9
Power Subsystem	46.0	14.6%	52.8
Harness	25.8	20.0%	30.9
Communications Subsystem	37.7	8.8%	41.0
GNC & AOCS Subsystem	44.5	12.6%	50.0
Structure and Mechanisms	83.0	20.0%	99.6
Thermal Subsystem	12.4	20.0%	14.8
Propulsion Subsystem	59.9	12.3%	67.3
Payload	20.0	19.0%	23.8
SPACECRAFT DRY TOTAL			399.2
System Mass Margin		20%	79.8
DRY TOTAL (incl. System Margin)			479.0
Propellant			351.9
SPACECRAFT WET MASS			831.0
Launch Adapter			0.0
WET MASS + LA			831.0
Launch Vehicle Capability - PSLV XL GTO			1074.0
Launch Vehicle Margin - PSLV XL GTO			243.0
Mass Margin % - PSLV XL GTO			22.6%

Roadmap

Technology Readiness Level

PLATFORM	TRL	Heritage	Expected Modifications
Payload			
Laser	3/4	Ground-based	Design and Space Qualification
Laser Optics	3/4	Ground-based	Design and Space Qualification
Impact Sensor	5	Rosetta (GIADA payload)	Modification and Space Qualification
Raman Spectrometer	5	ExoMars	Modification and Space Qualification
Power Subsystem			
Solar Array Assembly	5	IMM Cells - E3000 development	Further Cell Development/Qualification
Whipple Shield	5	ISS and ATV derivative	Significant modification
GNC & AOCS Subsystem			
Narrow Angle Camera	4	MarcoPolo-R	Continued development
Laser Rangefinder	9	ARP, ATV, HTV	Not tested for non-collaborative target

Roadmap

Technology	TRL	Activity	Target Date
Laser system	TRL4	Lab demonstration of improved diode stack efficiency	2014
	TRL4	Coherent combining for high power high efficiency laser	2016
	TRL5/6	Lab space qualification of fibre-diode coupled laser (vacuum, thermal, radiation tests)	2018
	TRL6	In space testing of adaptive optics	2018
	TRL7/8	In-space testing of fibre-diode coupled system	2020
Ablation process	TRL4	Lab experiments and model completion for both ablation and contamination	2013
	TRL5/6	In Earth orbit demonstrator with dummy asteroid.	2020
	TRL7/8	Asteroid material extraction and analysis mission	2025
	TRL8/9	AdAM	2027
In-space OD	TRL3	Concept demonstrated in simulation environment	2012
	TRL7/8	Multi asteroid discovery and tracking mission	2024
	TRL8/9	AdAM	2027
In-space rotation estimation	TRL3	Concept demonstrated in simulation environment	2012
	TRL6/7	In Earth orbit demonstration with dummy asteroid or space debris	2020
	TRL7/8	Multi asteroid discovery and tracking mission	2024
	TRL8/9	AdAM	2027
In-space deflection estimation	TRL3	Concept demonstrated in simulation environment	2012
	TRL6/7	In Earth orbit demonstration with dummy asteroid or space debris	2020
	TRL7/8	Asteroid material extraction and analysis mission	2024
	TRL8/9	AdAM	2027

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Questions?

Backup Slides

Back Up- Rotation Estimate FFT Approach

- Hirai et Al. 1998:

$$\mathbf{p}' = \mathbf{R}(\mathbf{k}_1, \theta_1) \mathbf{R}(\mathbf{k}_2, \theta_2) \hat{\mathbf{p}} + \mathbf{p}_0$$

$$\mathbf{p}' = \mathbf{a} \cos(\theta_1) + \mathbf{b} \sin(\theta_1) + \mathbf{c} \cos(\theta_2) + \mathbf{d} \sin(\theta_2) + \mathbf{e} \cos(\theta_1 + \theta_2) + \mathbf{f} \sin(\theta_1 + \theta_2) + \mathbf{g} \cos(\theta_1 - \theta_2) + \mathbf{h} \sin(\theta_1 - \theta_2) + \mathbf{i}$$

$$\mathbf{a} = -C_1 C_2 \mathbf{k}_1 + C_3 \mathbf{k}_2 \quad e = \{(1 + C_1) \hat{\mathbf{p}} + (C_1 C_3 - C_2) \mathbf{k}_1 - (C_2 + C_3) \mathbf{k}_2\} / 2$$

$$\mathbf{b} = C_3 (\mathbf{k}_1 \times \mathbf{k}_2) \quad f = \{-C_4 \mathbf{k}_1 - C_3 (\mathbf{k}_1 \times \mathbf{k}_2) + (\mathbf{k}_1 \times \hat{\mathbf{p}}) + (\mathbf{k}_2 \times \hat{\mathbf{p}})\} / 2$$

$$\mathbf{c} = -(C_1 C_3 - C_2) \mathbf{k}_2 \quad g = \{(1 + C_1) \hat{\mathbf{p}} + (C_1 C_3 - C_2) \mathbf{k}_1 + (C_2 - C_3) \mathbf{k}_2\} / 2$$

$$\mathbf{d} = C_4 \mathbf{k}_1 \quad h = \{C_4 \mathbf{k}_1 - C_3 (\mathbf{k}_1 \times \mathbf{k}_2) + (\mathbf{k}_1 \times \hat{\mathbf{p}}) - (\mathbf{k}_2 \times \hat{\mathbf{p}})\} / 2$$

$$\mathbf{i} = C_1 C_3 \mathbf{k}_1 + \mathbf{p}_0$$

$$C_1 = \mathbf{k}_1^T \mathbf{k}_2$$

$$C_2 = \mathbf{k}_1^T \hat{\mathbf{p}}$$

$$C_3 = \mathbf{k}_2^T \hat{\mathbf{p}}$$

$$C_4 = \mathbf{k}_1^T (\mathbf{k}_2 \times \hat{\mathbf{p}})$$

- a, b, ..., i can be obtained from the Fourier transform of the time sequence data of p'

$$f_1 \rightarrow \mathbf{a} = 2 / N \operatorname{Re}[P(f_1)]$$

$$f_2 \rightarrow \mathbf{c} = 2 / N \operatorname{Re}[P(f_1)]$$

$$\mathbf{i} = 1 / N \cdot P(0)$$

$$f_1 \rightarrow \mathbf{b} = -2 / N \operatorname{Im}[P(f_1)]$$

$$f_2 \rightarrow \mathbf{d} = -2 / N \operatorname{Im}[P(f_1)]$$

$$f_1 + f_2 \rightarrow \mathbf{e} = 2 / N \operatorname{Re}[P(f_1 + f_2)]$$

$$|f_1 - f_2| \rightarrow \mathbf{g} = 2 / N \operatorname{Re}[P(|f_1 - f_2|)]$$

$$f_1 + f_2 \rightarrow \mathbf{f} = -2 / N \operatorname{Im}[P(f_1 + f_2)]$$

$$|f_1 - f_2| \rightarrow \mathbf{h} = -2 / N \operatorname{Im}[P(|f_1 - f_2|)]$$

- Spin axes \mathbf{k}_1 \mathbf{k}_2 and centre of gravity \mathbf{p}_0

$$\mathbf{k}_1 = \frac{\mathbf{e} \times \mathbf{f}}{|\mathbf{e}|^2}$$

$$\mathbf{k}_2 = \frac{(\mathbf{e} + \mathbf{g} + \mathbf{c}) \times (\mathbf{f} - \mathbf{h} + \mathbf{d})}{|\mathbf{e} + \mathbf{g} + \mathbf{c}|^2}$$

$$\mathbf{p}_0 = \frac{(\mathbf{k}_1 \times \mathbf{k}_2)^T \times (\mathbf{a} \times \mathbf{k}_1)}{|\mathbf{e}|^2} \mathbf{k}_2 + \mathbf{a} + \mathbf{i}$$

Back Up- Proximity navigation and control

- Angular velocity

$$\mathbf{x}_{r_a} \times (\ddot{\mathbf{v}} \times \mathbf{x}_{r_a}) + 2\dot{\mathbf{x}}_{r_a} \times (\dot{\mathbf{v}} \times \mathbf{x}_{r_a}) = \mathbf{x}_{r_a} \times \mathbf{a}_{laser-local}$$

- Potential from ellipsoid body

$$U_{20+22} = \frac{\mu_A}{\delta r^3} \left(C_{20} \left(1 - \frac{3}{2} \cos^2 \gamma \right) + 3C_{22} \cos^2 \gamma \cos 2\lambda \right)$$

$$C_{20} = -\frac{1}{10} (2c_i^2 - a_i^2 - b_i^2)$$

$$C_{22} = \frac{1}{20} (a_i^2 - b_i^2)$$

- Perturbative forces

$$F_{Solar} = C_R S_{srp} \left(\frac{r_{AU}}{r_{sc}} \right)^2 A_M \frac{\mathbf{x}_a}{r_{sc}}; \quad F_{recoil} = \eta_{sys} S_{srp} \left(\frac{r_{AU}}{r_{sc}} \right)^2 A_M \frac{\mathbf{x}}{\delta r}; \quad F_{plume} = \rho_{plume} (\delta r) \bar{v}_{plume}^2 (\delta r) A_{eq} \frac{\mathbf{x}}{\delta r} \cdot \hat{i}$$

- Number of actuations

Back Δv imparted onto the asteroid

- Gauss' equations

$$\delta a = \frac{2a^2\gamma}{\mu} \delta v_t$$

$$\delta e = \frac{1}{v} \left[2(e + \cos f) \delta v_t - \frac{r}{a} \sin f \delta v_n \right]$$

$$\delta i = \frac{r \cos \vartheta}{h} \delta v_h$$

$$\delta \Omega = \frac{r \sin \vartheta}{h \sin i} \delta v_h$$

$$\delta \omega = \frac{1}{ev} \left[2 \sin f \delta v_t - \left(2e + \frac{r}{a} \cos f \right) \delta v_n - \frac{r \sin \vartheta \cos i}{h \sin i} \delta v_h \right]$$

- Variation in mean anomaly

through Gauss' equations

due to a variation in a

$$\delta M = -\frac{b}{eav} \left[2 \left(1 + \frac{e^2 r}{p} \right) \sin f \delta v_t - \frac{r}{a} \cos f \delta v_n \right] + \Delta n (t_{MOID} - t_d)$$

Back Δv imparted onto the asteroid

$$\begin{cases} \delta r(t_{measure}) = A_{measure\ nominal} \delta \alpha(t_{d-measure}) \\ \delta \alpha(t_{d-measure}) = G_d \delta v(t_d) \end{cases}$$

Proximal motion between nominal and deviated

Gauss' equations (also orbit perturbation can be included)

GNC-Estimating Δv imparted onto the asteroid

- Augmented state vector $[x, y, z, v_x, v_y, v_z, a_{laser}, a_{plume}]$
- Acceleration considered as bias (no time variation)

$$\dot{a}_{laser} = 0 + v_{laser}$$

$$\dot{a}_{plume} = 0 + v_{plume}$$

Why not Electric Propulsion from GTO?

- Moderate Mission ΔV from GTO of $\sim 1.4\text{km/s}$
 - Propellant savings from EP are not compelling
- Only have 3 years in total for SySNOVA:
 - EP for escape incurs a time and significant Δv penalty
 - Mass penalty for high thrust & power for rapid escape
- Every orbit in GTO passes through radiation belts
 - Need to escape quickly or accept high radiation dose
 - Mass (for faster escape) or Cost (radiation) penalty
- All up EP (for transfer & AOCS) is heavy & expensive
 - Separate EP (for transfer) & chemical RCS is inefficient and still expensive
- A combined CPS is significantly cheaper and simpler than EPS options

Why not LEO?

- PSLV to LEO also considered
 - Total available mass of 789-3760kg dependent on altitude and inclination of orbit
- The LISA PRM could be used in 2 ways:
 1. To provide all of the Δv to escape
 - Would need significant modification to accommodate fuel mass
 2. To provide as much Δv as possible with no modification with spacecraft providing remainder
 - Spacecraft mass is potentially over the design limit of PRM, again requiring modifications

Why not LEO?

- Escaping from LEO with a solid motor was also considered
- Several issues were identified
- No European solid motor exists
 - American solid motor would need to be used
- No European heritage for the use of solid motors
- Significant additional mass would be required
 - Structure between solid motor and spacecraft
 - Spin table
- Further unknown complexities that add mass

PSLV XL Mass Budget

SysNova Mass Budget	Current Mass (kg)	Design Maturity Margin (%)	Maximum Mass (kg)
Data Handling	17.1	10.9%	18.9
Power	68.8	16.4%	80.1
Communications	37.7	8.8%	41.0
GNC & AOCS	39.5	7.9%	42.5
Structure and Thermal	100.0	20.0%	120.0
Propulsion	59.9	12.3%	67.3
Payload	35.5	19.4%	42.4
SPACECRAFT DRY TOTAL	371.4	15.2%	427.9
Harness	30.0	20.0%	35.9
DRY TOTAL (incl. Harness)			463.8
System Mass Margin		20.0%	92.8
DRY TOTAL (incl. 20% System Margin)			556.6
Propellant			442.2
SPACECRAFT WET MASS			998.8
Launch Vehicle Capability - PSLV GTO			1074.0
Launch Vehicle Margin - PSLV GTO			75.2
Mass Margin % - PSLV GTO			7.0%

Laser Range Finder

- ESA ILT – undergoing programmes miniaturization of LIDAR technology – Jena Optroniks and ABSL

Roadmap

Δ in ILT (LRF-only) Ground test on non-collaborative target (asteroid mockup)

Roadmap

- LRF
 - BB Model tested
 - Range (at 5000 Km)
 - Accuracy <10 cm
 - Scanning and processing are the heavy/power-hungry
 - Sensor head 1.7 Kg
 - Power (30 W) – moving mirror

- Jena ILT Tested in GNC testbed in real time with FF Algorithms (PLATFORM)

Figure 9. HARVD development and validation environments

Figure 11. Sensors mounted on the mock-up

Roadmap for GNC technology maturation

- Optical Navigation
 - Proba-3 (main system and RV experiments), Rosetta experience
- LRF
 - ILT, Prototype, test with PLATFORM
 - 2013 – 4 developments in Europe (GSTP Debris Removal, Science – Marco Polo (hayabusa-like 3 beams), ABSL, NEPTEC? still developing for Lunar Lander, DLR supporting qualification of Jena's RVS
- GNC algorithms for RV / Asteroid state identification / FEIC
 - Virtual simulations (PANGU) , tests with PLATFORM
- Test of full system in orbital debris removal

Autonomy

- Autonomous GNC reduced to a minimum – NO AutoNAV!
 - NO autonomous detection, NO autonomous GNC up to 10 Km, Hold Points, Modular Design
- Imperative for Station Keeping (non-stable station keeping point)
- Same algorithms and techniques widely used for Pointing (Attitude Control)
- GNC for Close Approach (<10 Km)
 - 6 days
 - Hold Points waiting for “Go” from ground
 - Quick response is needed for safety (SRP moves SC 5 Km in 3 days)
 - Final segment is supervised from ground
 - Heritage of procedures from PROBA; ATV

Collision Avoidance

- Not a typical NEO mission
 - Gravity pull from asteroid $< 2 \mu\text{N}$
 - SRP $\sim 40 \mu\text{N}$
 - **Collision Avoidance Design – SC is 10 m offset to asteroid's orbital plane**
 - (offset has negligible effect of $< 1 \text{ pN}$ due to differential gravity)
- Larger Concerns:
 - Evaporation
 - No illumination angle (SC is pushed to the dark side of the asteroid)
- This happens only in case of failure (FDIR field)
- **Passive Safety – Worst case – loss of control (position, attitude, tumbling)**

Trailing Configuration

- No Collision – Safe with 25% to 100% SRP , 2 day propagation

Radial Configuration Configuration

- No Collision – Safe with 25% to 100% SRP
- Safe with offset of 10 meters

Rel. distance no control - radial + out of plane comp.

Radial Configuration Configuration

- Worst case – error in position $\Delta\text{position} = 1\text{ m}$. $\Delta\text{velocity} = 1\text{ mm/s}$, 25% SRP

CEAM / FDIR

- Detection of failure / Contingency
 - Fault/Failure in component detected by component (hardware) – sensor actuator failure flag
 - Incoherent measurements/data detected in cross-checking (pre-processing) in the GNC chain
 - Contingency – raw algorithms for CAEM
 - LRF raw measurement exceeds limit
 - SC spans more than 10000 pixels in WAC
 - Contingency – GNC solution shows phase angle >30 deg (radial) or > 120 (trailing)

- Classification → Contingency plan / FDIR
 - No failures, immediate recovery to operational conditions
 - Supervised recovery (boost in Sun direction - 3 days safe, 14 days safe), send to further away SK
 - Safe mode with 3 months of opportunity
 - Safe mode to equilibrium point
 - Worst-Case – Attitude Control with RCS, Sun-Pointing, Boost of towards* Sun

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Safe Hold Points

- No terminator Orbits – asteroid gravity \ll SRP
- No stable orbits due to SRP
- However, **~615 Km** distance, gravity gradient balances SRP
- In case of failure ~ 0.4 m/s boost brings SC in 30 days to point where breaking leaves the SC in an equilibrium orbit with little drift.

Non-Critical CEAM - Reconfiguration

- Hops – 50 mm/s provides 14 days for diagnostic/reconfiguration

- Pure CEAM (no failure) -> 3 day hop
- Failure in redundant system (eg LRF) -> Reconfiguration (ranging from camera) 14 day hop
- Failure in Critical system (eg Attitude Control, RCS) -> 300 mm/s hop to SAFE orbit

